

RESEARCH ATTITUDE AND RESEARCH ENGAGEMENT AMONG THIRD YEAR COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the key domain of research attitude that most effectively predicts research engagement among third-year college students. Employing a predictive correlation research design, the researchers administered the adopted survey questionnaires both in face-to-face and online platforms to collect comprehensive data. Statistical tools such as Weighted Mean, Pearson-r, and Multiple Regression Analysis were utilized for data analysis. Results indicated a high level of research attitude among the respondents, reflecting a positive overall disposition toward research. Concurrently, the research engagement level was also notably high, indicating active involvement in research activities. Moreover, a moderate positive correlation was observed between research attitude and research engagement, affirming the interconnected nature of these variables. Notably, the analysis of research attitude indicators revealed that a positive attitude emerged as the most influential domain in predicting research engagement among third-year college students. These findings provide valuable insights into the factors shaping students' engagement in research and underscore the significance of cultivating a positive research attitude for heightened research involvement.

Keywords: *research attitude, research engagement, predictive correlation, third year college students*

INTRODUCTION

Research is of paramount importance across various fields and disciplines, playing a crucial role in advancing knowledge, fostering innovation, and addressing complex challenges (Bammer, 2020). In higher education institutions, students are required to come up with a research paper focusing on problems, issues or topics relative to their interest (Papanastasiou, 2013). To note, students often face several challenges when it comes to engaging in research activities. One significant issue is the struggle to navigate and comprehend the vast and sometimes overwhelming volume of available information. The abundance of resources, coupled with the need for critical evaluation and synthesis of relevant literature, can be daunting for students (Safitri, 2021). Additionally, limited access to scholarly databases, inadequate research skills, and a lack of familiarity with proper citation practices may hinder their ability to gather and incorporate credible sources into their work (Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020). Time management is another common challenge, as students often juggle multiple academic and personal responsibilities, making it difficult to dedicate sufficient time to in-depth research (Wolters & Brady, 2021).

Several conducted studies on research engagement have consistently highlighted its critical role in fostering academic success and personal development among students. The results of these studies consistently show a positive correlation between high levels of research engagement and improved academic performance, critical thinking skills, and a deeper understanding of course content (Wang & Degol, 2014). Moreover, research engagement has been linked to increased motivation, enhanced problem-solving abilities, and a heightened sense of intellectual curiosity. These findings underscore the importance of incorporating research engagement activities in educational programs, as they contribute not only to the academic achievements of students but also to the cultivation of essential skills and qualities that are invaluable for their future endeavors in both academic and professional spheres.

Despite the considerable body of research exploring the individual dimensions of research attitude and research engagement among students, a noticeable research gap exists in understanding the nuanced interplay between these constructs, particularly in the context of higher education (McCormick, et.al., 2013). While there is acknowledgment of the positive relationship between positive research attitudes and heightened research engagement, there is a scarcity of studies that delve into the specific domains of research attitude that significantly contribute to and predict the level of research engagement among students (Brew & Mantai, 2017).

Addressing these obstacles would provide valuable insights for educators and institutions aiming to design targeted interventions to enhance research engagement. Such a focused investigation would not only bridge a current gap in understanding but also contribute to the development of more effective strategies for promoting research culture and student involvement in academic research endeavors.

Research Questions

The primary goal of this research was to determine which domain of Research Attitude can best predict the Research Engagement among third year college students of Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology- Trento Satellite Campus.

Specifically, it attended to attain the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of student's Research Attitude in terms of:
 - 1.1. Relevance to Life;
 - 1.2. Research Anxiety;
 - 1.3. Research Difficulties; and
 - 1.4. Positive Attitude.
2. To identify the level of student's Research Engagement in terms of:
 - 2.1. Affective Category;
 - 2.2. Behavioral Category;
 - 2.3. Benefits of the Course;
 - 2.4. Cognitive Category; and
 - 2.5. Research Self-Efficacy.
3. To determine the significant relationship between the Research Attitude and Research Engagement of students in Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology- Trento Satellite Campus.
4. To determine which of the domains of Research Attitude can best predict the Research Engagement of student in Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology- Trento Satellite Campus.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed predictive correlational research design. This research design aims to examine the relationships between variables and predict future outcomes. Further, the respondents of the study were the third-year college students from five programs namely, BEED, BSED Mathematics, BSED English, AB English Language, and BS Applied Mathematics. To determine the sample size of the ongoing study, Rao soft calculator was utilized. Out of 260, there were 156 third-year college students who participated in the study through stratified random sampling and lottery method. In addition, two sets of survey questionnaires were personally distributed to the identified respondents. To analyze the gathered data, Weighted Mean, Pearson-r and Multiple Regression analysis were used.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Research Attitude

Research Attitude	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Level
Relevance to Life	3.18	0.55	High
Research Anxiety	3.77	0.73	High
Research Difficulties	3.76	0.70	High
Positive Attitude	3.72	0.63	High
Overall	3.61	0.438	High

Table 2. Level of Research Engagement

Research Engagement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Level
Research Self Efficacy	3.40	0.55	High
Affective Category	3.40	0.69	High
Cognitive Category	3.65	0.59	High
Behavioral Category	3.81	0.68	High
Benefits of the Course	3.96	0.61	High
Overall	3.64	0.448	High

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Research Attitude and Research Engagement

Research Attitude	Research Engagement	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Remarks
	Overall Mean	0.319**	0.000	Highly Significant

Table 4. Multiple Regression Analysis in determining which domain of Research Attitude

Research Attitude	Standardized Coefficient	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Remarks
Relevance to Life	0.260	4.542	0.000	Highly Significant
Research Anxiety	-0.242	-2.881	0.005	Significant

Research Difficulties	-0.104	1.262	0.209	Not Significant
Positive Attitude	0.724	13.103	0.000	Highly Significant

DISCUSSION

The research attitude of third-year college students obtained an overall mean of 3.61 with a standard deviation of 0.438, indicates a generally positive orientation towards research-related activities. The mean value, falling above the midpoint of the scale, suggests that, on average, students tend to exhibit favorable attitudes and perceptions toward engaging in research endeavors. The standard deviation of 0.438, a measure of the variability or dispersion in the data, implies a relatively tight clustering around the mean, indicating a consistent and cohesive trend in the students' research attitudes. This finding suggests a shared positive disposition among the surveyed students, emphasizing a collective readiness and interest in embracing research activities. Overall, these results provide valuable insights into the prevailing attitudes of third-year college students towards research, which can inform educational strategies and interventions to further cultivate and enhance their research-oriented mindset. The result agrees with the study of Cheng and Yau (2019) who stated that students who had positive attitudes towards research were more likely to engage in research activities and produce higher quality research outputs.

On the other hand, the research engagement of third-year college students, as indicated by an overall mean of 3.64 with a standard deviation of 0.448, suggests a relatively high level of engagement within the study population. The mean score of 3.64, on a scale where higher values typically denote greater engagement, indicates that, on average, the students exhibit a positive disposition toward research activities. The standard deviation of 0.448, a measure of the dispersion of scores around the mean, suggests a relatively narrow distribution, indicating that the majority of students cluster around the mean score. This homogeneity in scores implies a consistent level of research engagement among the third-year college students. Overall, the findings suggest a commendable level of interest and active participation in research-related endeavors within this student cohort, showcasing a positive trend in fostering a research-oriented academic environment. The finding is in consonance with the study of Horowitz and Christopher (2013) who averred that engagement in research activities, including hands-on projects and collaborative initiatives, contributes significantly to the overall educational experience. Additionally, Bond, et.al., (2020) stated that exploration of student engagement in higher education provides insights into the transformative effects of research involvement on students' intellectual and personal growth.

With regards the relationship of the two variables, it indicates a statistically significant relationship between research attitude and research engagement among third-year college students. It obtained an overall r-value of 0.319, the positive sign suggests

a generally favorable association between these two variables. The p-value of 0.000, being less than the conventional significance level of 0.05, reinforces the assertion that this relationship is not due to random chance but is indeed statistically significant. In practical terms, this implies that as research attitude scores increase, there is a corresponding increase in research engagement among the third-year college students in the study. The findings underscore the importance of fostering a positive research attitude to enhance and promote active participation in research activities among students at this academic level. This statistical significance provides empirical support for the premise that cultivating a favorable research attitude can positively influence and contribute to increased research engagement among third-year college students (Ommering, et.al., 2020).

The Multiple Regression analysis results reveal that the domain of positive attitude within research attitude significantly predicts the research engagement of third-year college students. The standardized coefficient, with a value of 0.724, indicates a strong positive relationship between research attitude and research engagement. This coefficient represents the change in standard deviation units of the research engagement for each standard deviation increase in the independent variable particularly in positive attitude domain. The associated t-value of 13.103, along with a p-value of 0.000, reinforces the statistical significance of this predictive relationship. In other words, this suggests that as positive attitude scores increase, there is a substantial and statistically significant increase in research engagement among third-year college students. These findings underscore the pivotal role of fostering a research attitude, particularly in the domain of positive attitude, as a potent predictor of heightened research engagement among students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it has been concluded that the level of research attitude among respondents is high which means that their research attitude is positive. On the other hand, the level of research engagement is rated as high which means that the respondents are engaged in research activities. It was also found that there is positive correlation between research attitude and research engagement which implies that any increase or decrease in research attitude has a corresponding increase or decrease in research engagement. Lastly, a positive attitude was revealed as the best predictor of research engagement.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, it is strongly recommended that educational institutions and instructors may continue to cultivate a positive research attitude among third-year college students. Fostering a positive disposition towards research, particularly emphasizing the domain of positive attitudes, may be integrated into academic programs

and curricula. Implementing targeted interventions, workshops, and mentorship programs aimed at enhancing students' research attitudes is crucial. Additionally, educators may emphasize the practical relevance of research, showcasing its impact on personal and academic growth. Simultaneously, institutions may also continue to create an environment that encourages active research engagement, providing opportunities for hands-on experiences, collaborative projects, and mentorship. By aligning pedagogical approaches with the promotion of positive research attitudes and offering diverse avenues for engagement, educational institutions can effectively nurture a culture of research enthusiasm among third-year college students, fostering their holistic development and preparing them for future academic and professional pursuits.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In compliance with ethical standards in conducting research, the researchers established guidelines and principles such as informed consent, confidentiality, privacy, and minimizing harm. Researchers obtain informed consent from participants, ensuring they fully understand the nature and purpose of the study, as well as any potential risks involved. Additionally, researchers respect participants' privacy and confidentiality by safeguarding their personal information and ensuring anonymity whenever possible. Furthermore, researchers strived to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to respondents throughout the research process. By upholding these ethical standards, researchers can foster trust and uphold the ethical principles fundamental to the pursuit of knowledge.

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